

METHODOLOGY FOR ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT LEARNING ACTIVITIES IN THE ACADEMIC LYCEUMS OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS

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Annotation. This article addresses the issues of effectively organizing independent learning activities of students in the academic lyceums under the Ministry of Internal Affairs. In particular, it presents proposals and recommendations for organizing independent learning activities through a web-based platform.

Keywords: independent learning activity, academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, students, web platform, organization.

Today, in the educational process, fostering students' ability to acquire knowledge independently, engage in self-directed learning, and develop personal growth skills is regarded as an essential task. In particular, in the academic lyceums under the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the proper organization of independent learning activities plays a crucial role in preparing the younger generation who will work in law enforcement agencies in the future. This is because such students should not only master theoretical knowledge but also acquire the ability to make independent decisions in practical situations, demonstrate initiative, and assume responsibility.

Traditional classroom processes do not sufficiently foster students' skills of independent thinking and inquiry. Therefore, in organizing independent learning, it is crucial to make use of modern information and communication technologies, particularly web-based platforms. An educational process organized through a web platform enables students to independently plan their time, conduct self-directed inquiry, assess their knowledge, and improve their competencies.

In the education system of Uzbekistan, the widespread introduction of a digital learning environment and the development of opportunities for independent learning are considered one of the priority directions of state policy. In particular, organizing the process of independent knowledge acquisition in a professionally oriented manner in the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs ensures the effective performance of students in their future careers. The use of web-based platforms to enhance the effectiveness of independent learning, on the one hand, strengthens the transparency and monitoring of the educational process, and on the other hand, fosters in students a culture of using information technologies [1].

From this perspective, the scientific and methodological study of the issues related to organizing independent learning activities on the basis of web platforms, the determination of their pedagogical foundations, and the development of mechanisms for their practical implementation represent urgent scientific and pedagogical tasks today [2].

To conduct research on this issue, we first came to the conclusion that it is necessary to analyze the concepts of independent education, independent learning activity, and web platform, as well as the views expressed by researchers regarding these concepts.

In this regard, as Y.R.Azzamov states, “independent learning is not only a form of education but also a culture of continuous learning, inquiry, and self-development throughout life. Its proper organization requires the joint activity of teachers and learners, a clearly planned methodology, and a fair assessment system” [3]. According to Ye.V.Minina, “an individual’s independent learning is a purposeful and systematic cognitive activity necessary to solve problems arising at different stages of life activities, not only to improve the level of education but also to satisfy personal needs for acquiring second and third specializations” [4]. A. Paranthaman notes that “independent learning activity is a type of activity aimed at forming, deepening, and consolidating the learner’s knowledge and skills, which includes self-management, self-monitoring, and self-assessment, and is carried out without external guidance or with minimal assistance” [5].

According to Z.Lein, “independent learning activity is a form of educational activity that involves the learner independently planning, performing educational tasks, analyzing results, and generalizing, which requires activity, independence, and initiative in the process of knowledge acquisition” [6].

Based on the analysis of the scientific and methodological works of the above-mentioned researchers and scholars, we have developed the following definition of the concept of independent learning activity of an academic lyceum student.

The independent learning activity of an academic lyceum student is a form of educational activity consciously carried out through self-management, planning, inquiry, and evaluation, aimed at mastering, analyzing, and creatively applying theoretical and practical knowledge, based on the learner’s individual needs, interests, and intellectual potential oriented towards professional development.

In today’s context, as the education system is stepping into the stage of digital transformation, the effective organization of independent learning activities of academic lyceum students cannot be imagined without the use of digital technologies [1]. Digital tools provide learners with opportunities to work independently on the acquired knowledge, quickly access necessary resources, exercise self-monitoring, and analyze results. In our view, through digital technologies, particularly web-based platforms, students can design their independent tasks, collaborate remotely, and maintain their educational achievements in the form of a portfolio. This serves as an essential factor in developing their metacognitive skills.

In this regard, according to H.O.Jo‘rayev and F.G‘.Tohirova, “web platforms offer features and functions that align with various teaching methods and goals, making them indispensable in modern educational strategies. From interactive modules and simulations to collaborative projects and real-time feedback mechanisms, these platforms create dynamic learning environments that simulate authentic professional scenarios” [7].

Based on the provided definitions and the analysis of scholarly research, it can be stated that the use of web-based platforms plays a crucial role in organizing the independent learning activities of students in the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

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